

USE OF NATIONAL SPIRITUAL VALUES IN ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL EVENTS IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Adilova Naila

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute, 2nd-year master's student of Pre-school education

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Abstract. *In this article, the formation of educational activities for children with the help of national values, the formation of content at the level of children's aesthetic culture, their conscious activity, level of knowledge, faith - historical experiences, traditions, traditions and customs, our national values It is about the study of mothers, customs and traditions, family, preschool education organization, community, and the work done in neighborhoods.*

Keywords: *parent, family, child, value, activity, culture, work, duty, tradition, custom, tradition, education.*

Interests and abilities of children of preschool age are manifested in the practical and theoretical dialogue of educators with a specific goal, provided that spiritual resources and the requirements and needs of the present time are provided for. It is necessary to understand its essence when educating preschool children on the basis of universal human values. Values are divided into several types according to their essence. In particular, a person and his life are the highest value. That is why honoring human dignity, improving his life, developing his knowledge and cultural level, maintaining his health, and protecting his life are the main directions of our state's policy. All of the fundamental changes and reforms taking place in our society make people's lives full, rich, beautiful, people feel truly free, the results of their work, their destiny, their own is aimed at ensuring that the country becomes the owner. The events that surround a person, including national spirituality, that have special significance and value for a specific person or social group, or for a specific nation, or for the whole of humanity, are called value. National values are the images, traditions, qualities, morals and manners of a particular people, lifestyle, holidays, buildings, national clothes, household items that are worthy of respect by the majority of the people. , it is said that they make a living. For example, the Uzbek national values are hard work, hospitality, kindness and gentleness, enthusiasm and obedience, getting along with people of different categories, forgiveness, thinking and thinking, peace-loving. is considered

The spirituality of each nation is based not only on its national factors, but also as a result of the influence of universal values. In this sense, one of the spiritual and moral foundations of strengthening our national independence is loyalty to universal values². In fact, the roots of our national spirituality are connected with the traditions of creative assimilation of the highest values of other peoples. If we approach the history of our spirituality and culture from this point of view, we will witness that Uzbek national art, poetry, and science benefited from Arab, Persian, and even Greek culture in the past. So, there are enough grounds to talk about national and universal spirituality. The question of the relationship between national and universal spirituality helps to understand this problem in depth. This issue is a special area of expression of individuality and commonality. The spiritual image of a nation is expressed in its national consciousness and spirit. It is a legal phenomenon that the spiritual image of each nation is enriched depending on the

material, socio-historical conditions of the society. National consciousness, which is an important element of spirituality, is relatively independent, it can actively influence the fundamental change of the material and spiritual image of society. National consciousness and its formation takes place, first of all, at the heart of national awakening. National consciousness and its understanding require each person to know his nationality, his national history, culture, heritage, traditions, and language correctly and thoroughly. If national affiliation and all its aspects are scientifically based in people's imagination, it is national self-awareness. When the awareness of national identity takes a scientific and political shape and rises to the level of a manual for social action, it will undoubtedly become a national ideology. National ideology serves as the main weapon protecting the interests of national culture, values and spirituality.

The perfection of a person is determined, first of all, by his spiritual maturity. In our opinion, the spirituality of a person is a spiritual process that is manifested in the practical activity of his thoughts, intentions, ideas, theories and teachings with a positive content in his mind. It is worth noting that, on the basis of the spirituality of a person, it should be taken into account that he understands the content of thoughts, intentions, ideas, theories and teachings that have a positive content. So, the spirituality of the Uzbek people is to be truthful and fair, to block the path of ignorance and vulgarity, humanity, kindness, enlightenment, friendship, courage, brotherhood, hospitality, calls for inculcating human qualities such as purity, good manners, honesty, and patriotism.

Preschool education serves to ensure the comprehensive development of children, taking into account their age and individual characteristics. Preschool education organizations educate children in all aspects. The first age in a child's life is the most important period, and it is in this period that the child's spiritual, physical, moral, and aesthetic development is the foundation.

In pre-school educational organizations, raising children as well-rounded, well-rounded individuals is mainly formed in the process of classes, games, walks, observations, and cultural and household activities. Such direction is effective, especially on the basis of national values. During the traditions, which are our national values, children's thoughts, views, feelings, desire, will, thinking, worldview, and moral culture develop.

In pre-school educational organizations, our young generations should understand the interests of the country, the people, the nation and the Motherland, increase their glory, study science and culture, the rich heritage, history, religion and values of our ancestors, and properly evaluate them. the activities of our educators are of great importance.

Regarding the life and creative path of scientists, writers and poets on the topic of the harmony of nationality and national meaningful values in preschool education organization in educating preschool children on the basis of national values, effectively instilling national-spiritual, ethnic values into the minds of young people It would be appropriate if we could show the videos related to creativity.

With the help of our national values that interest children, slide films, colorful picture books, cultural recreation centers for children, organizations (cinema theater, folk troupes, folk theaters, art palaces, cultural centers, etc.) provides an opportunity to satisfy their interests. It has a positive effect on the overall formation of aspects of moral culture. However, children's household activities are not only armed with theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications that have emerged through national values, but also that they can freely, consciously and fairly solve the concepts of moral culture, express their attitudes about them, they are also

taught to be able to draw correct conclusions and to preserve, preserve, love, and ensure their longevity.

Children develop concepts such as "Me and my friends", "I am hospitable", "My good qualities", "I am a good child". On the basis of such concepts, children can see and feel human interests on the basis of traditions, traditions, customs, learn the culture of the national people, feel the need to understand their identity, correctly understand the role of human labor, humanitarianism. , kindness, faith, loving and honoring one's Motherland, love for the Motherland, loyalty, parents, relatives, respect for the elderly, taking care of the little ones, and being kind and generous to others such qualities are formed.

The organization of educational activities in preschool educational organizations is organized as follows, depending on the needs and interests of children:

1. Being able to set the right goal in the process of activity;
2. Cultural environment, directing activities to the formation of cultural, moral and spiritual values in children;
3. It is to ensure the balance between the content, form, style, method and means of the activity.

Therefore, in the formation of moral qualities and culture, the organization of the educational system - a cultural environment, a model consisting of stages of cultural activity, creates an opportunity to understand them in all respects and preserve national values. Another characteristic of children's spiritual world is that they consider adults as authoritative people, role models, take advice, imitate, and make sure that they get any help when needed. can't tell a secret. The sample plays the role of the main source for imitation. A personal example is a set of behaviors and other activities of adults that influence the mind and behavior of the growing young generation as a form of education. The educational influence of adults as role models is important because they are a living source for children to imitate. The following conclusions follow from the above considerations:

Value is not a unique feature or property of any event, event or thing, but its essence, in turn, it is a necessary condition for the existence and existence of this or that object of existence.

Values can be divided into national and universal, class or religious values, as well as values specific to people's age and professional characteristics, depending on their place in the life of the society, the nation, and their social character.

National values are a philosophical concept that expresses the unique characteristics, properties, signs, and symptoms of each nation, and represents its contribution and share to the treasure of national cultural heritage formed in the process of social development. Universal values represent the values that are common to representatives of all nations.

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